

the 9:7 ratio with a X^2 value of 2.29, nonsignificant at 1% level. Results confirmed the hypothesis that the height variability of the cross results from digenic segregation with complementary gene effects because each parent has one

of the dominant genes. Segregates had from early to medium growth duration and there was no obvious association between plant height and growth duration.

The shortest plants in the segregating

population were much shorter than the shortest parent and are double recessives, making them of great significance as representatives of a new source of dwarfing obtained by combining two recessive genes. □

Ratoon performance of some short-duration rice cultures

K. Karunakaran, M. B. Jalajakumari, and P. Sreedevi, Regional Agricultural Research Station, Pattambi, Kerala, India

Twenty rice varieties constituting the ninth International Rice Yield Nursery

(early) were grown in three replications at Pattambi during the 1981 kharif. Seedlings were transplanted at 15 cm × 10 cm spacing and received 70-35-35 kg NPK/ha. The main crop was harvested to leave 15-cm-tall stubble and entries were assessed for ratoon performance. The ratoon crop was not fertilized or sprayed.

It was not irrigated but 625 mm of rain fell over 38 rainy days.

Varietal differences in the ratoon yields were significant. Five IRRI lines—IR9209-48-3-2, IR9761-19-1, IR13427-40-2-3-3, IR13429-109-2-2-1, and IR13429-287-3—were promising (see table). □

Main crop and ratoon performance of some rice varieties at Pattambi, India.

Variety	Duration (days)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
BAU2-3-43	108	56	3.2	0.1
BKN7033-13-1-1-3-2	108	56	3.8	0.2
BPT1235	110	54	4.4	0.1
BR109-74-2-2-2	119	45	3.7	0.2
BR161-2B-58	117	47	3.5	0.2
Chianung Sen yu 13	113	51	3.6	0.4
IR9209-48-3-2	104	60	4.9	0.3
IR9761-19-1	103	61	4.9	0.3
IR9828-91-2-3	108	56	4.0	0.1
IR13427-40-2-3-3	113	51	4.6	0.5
IR13427-60-1-3-2-2	103	61	4.8	0.2
IR13429-109-2-2-1	108	56	4.6	0.4
IR13429-196-1	108	56	4.9	0.2
IR13429-287-3	113	51	4.8	0.3
MRC603-303	109	55	3.7	0.2
MTU34 19	116	48	3.6	0.0
Taichung Sen Yu 285	113	51	3.6	0.4
TNAU1756	103	61	3.8	0.1
IR36	108	56	4.2	0.2
KAU23332-2	113	51	4.5	0.1
CD ($P=0.05$)	—	—	0.55	0.21

Audiovisual cropping systems research modules

IRRI is producing a planned 45-module series of audiovisual lessons in cropping systems research, to include modules on: site selection and description, improved cropping systems design, preproduction testing, and component technology development and evaluation. Two modules, The morphology of maize and An introduction to cropping systems, are available for purchase. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publication Dept., Division R, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Promising TKM6 rice mutants

S. R. Sree Rangasamy and C. R. Anandakumar, School of Genetics, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

TKM6 (GEB24/Co 18 hybrid derivative) mutants were isolated after gamma irradiation and treatment with chemical mutagens ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS)

and di-ethyl sulfate (DES) either singly or in combination. Several dwarf mutants were isolated from the different treatments in M2 generation. Among them, three dwarf macromutants were identified as promising and grown through M3 and M4 (see table).

The dwarf mutant obtained with a 30 kR gamma ray dose was early maturing and had reduced leaf area, grain size,

and total dry matter production, but higher per day production, chlorophyll content, number of grains per panicle, and harvest index. The mutant obtained by combining treatments of 35 kR gamma rays + 30 mM EMS had greater leaf area, chlorophyll content, and per day productivity than the control. The third mutant, obtained with a 35 kR gamma ray dose, yielded higher than the